

The Extent of Internet Addiction among Students of Library and Information Science in some Universities in Nigeria.

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to investigate the extent of internet addiction among undergraduate students of Library and Information Science in some universities in Nigeria. This study collected data from 305 undergraduate students of Library and Information Science (LIS) in two universities in Nigeria using questionnaire. The study revealed that the undergraduate students of LIS used the internet for reasons such as enter chat rooms, connecting to social media platforms, to do course or assignment, watch videos, play mobile games, download music and videos, email communications, and Instagram. The results show that the students used the internet several times a day for different activities. The study found that the extent of internet addiction among LIS students is high, with internet addiction rate of 84.9%. Out of the number, 43.3% students reported mild addiction, 35.4% students reported moderate addiction and 6.2% reported severe addiction. The findings will be useful to education authorities as considering the increasing trend of IA in the recent years, the high prevalence of IA in students therefore calls for authorities to develop a national policy for the use of the internet among students. If this is not addressed as a priority, the country must anticipate a large population dependent on the internet, requiring medical attention. The findings will also provide significant implications for counsellors as predictors of internet addiction as required for delivering a focused intervention geared towards addressing the associated factors.

Keywords – Internet addiction, social networking, undergraduate students, LIS, Universities, Nigeria.

Introduction

The use of the internet has transformed the world in terms of information sharing, business opportunities, communication, learning, relationships, socialization, shopping, and entertainment, all now accessible with a single click (Naughton, 2016). The use of the Internet is highly individualized. The healthy way of using it is to accomplish a planned objective within a reasonable period with no behavioural or intellectual distress. Some individuals succeed in limiting their internet use whereas others cannot regulate themselves (Diomidous, Chardalias, & Magita, 2016). In general, Kuss (2013) reported that the main reason why youths are at particular risk of internet addiction is that they spend most of their time on online gaming and social applications like online social networking such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter and telegrams, and so on. Campbell, (2003) described “addiction” as excessive thoughts about and desire to perform a behaviour, excessive time spent to plan and engage in the behaviour, and possibly recover from its effects (e.g., from “hangovers”), and less time spent on other activities. The American Society of Addiction Medicine (ASAM) (2021) defines addiction as “a treatable, chronic medical disease involving complex interactions among brain circuits, genetics, the environment, and an individual’s life experiences.

People with addiction use substances or engage in behaviour that becomes compulsive and often continue despite harmful consequences” (p.1). Addicted to the internet in question are addicted to games, cybersex addiction, online social networking addiction (Starcevic & Aboujaoude, 2017). The rapid integration of the internet into global societies has posed new challenges related to the convenience of accessing aspects of the Internet that can be highly rewarding (e.g., gaming, social networking, pornography) (Mathew & Krishnan, 2020). One such issue is a behavioural phenotype called internet addiction (IA), which is conceptualized as an impulse control problem characterized by an inability to inhibit internet use to the extent that the usage has an adverse impact on major life domains (e.g., interpersonal relations, physical health) (Cheng & Li, 2014). In the context of this study, addiction simply means excessive time students spend on the internet. Misuse of the Internet has become a health concern worldwide and is growing swiftly and steadily.

Studies have shown that internet addiction is more prevalent among young people (Wong et al., 2015, Kamal & Kamal, 2018). Higher education students are especially vulnerable to developing dependence on the internet, more than most other segments of the society (Shapira et al. 2003). This can be attributed to several factors including the following: availability of time; ease of use; unlimited access to the internet; the psychological and developmental characteristics of young adulthood; limited or no parental supervision; an expectation of internet/computer use implicitly if not explicitly, as some courses are internet-dependent, from assignments and projects to communication with peers and mentors; the internet offering a route of escape from exam stress (Kamal & Kamal, 2018), all of which make internet overuse a significant cause of concern for parents and faculty. The internet can play a significant role in the lives of the undergraduate student as its use can complement the resources and services of the library and enhance their learning and academic performance when used with restraint especially for academic purposes. Despite the benefits students can derive from the Internet when used in moderation, the researchers’ personal observation has revealed that most students indulge in use of the internet on their smartphones while in the classroom taking lectures. This indulgence on internet use while the user should be fully devoted to lectures and learning is symptomatic of internet addiction. Excessive use of internet also affects the academic achievements of students (Hassan, et al 2020; Hsieh, 2019). Students addicted to the internet are more involved in it than their studies, and hence they have poor academic performance (Frangos, Fragkos & Kiohos 2010). Although internet addiction is reported to be associated with various personal, social and psychological factors in the literature, to the best of our knowledge, only few studies have been conducted to estimate the extent internet addiction on undergraduate students in Nigeria.

The present study aims to fill the gap. To achieve this, three research questions are raised to guide the study. They are:

Research Questions

RQ1. What are the reasons the LIS students in Enugu State University of Science and Technology and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education use the internet?

RQ2. How frequent do the LIS students in Enugu State University of Science and Technology and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education use the internet?

RQ3. What is the extent of internet addiction among the undergraduate students of LIS in Enugu State University of Science and Technology and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education?

Literature review

Internet addiction among students

Internet addiction can be defined as spending too much time on the internet, accompanied by psychological dependence on overuse of the Internet (Hsieh, 2019). Internet use is one of the most important tools of our present-day society whose impact is felt on students such as increased use of internet. It brings change in mood, an inability to control the amount of time spent with the internet, withdrawal symptoms when not engaged, a diminishing social life, and adverse work or academic consequences, and it also affects self-esteem of the students (Wang, et al. 2019; Mathew & Krishnan, 2020). With the advancement in media and technologies, internet has emerged as an effective tool in eliminating human geographical barriers. With the availability and mobility of new media, internet addiction has emerged as a potential problem in young people which refers to excessive computer use that interferes with their daily life. IA can reduce the young generation's productivity and cause cognitive dysfunction, poor academic performance and physical, mental and behavioural Disturbances (Mathew & Krishnan, 2020).

Misuse of the internet has become a health concern worldwide and is growing swiftly and steadily. The field of internet addiction has experienced significant debates over the years. At present, there are many uncertainties regarding the conceptualization of IA as a disorder, including internet gaming disorder (Wang, et al. 2019). IA usually refers to a persistent and recurrent maladaptive behaviour, causing distress and significant functional impairments (Young, 1998). Internet addiction is concerned with overuse or excessive use of the internet, and some researchers call it internet addiction disorder (Feng et al., 2019). IA involves different types of online behaviours, such as online gaming, online shopping, online pornography, online gambling, and social media use (Mathew & Krishnan, 2020). Kumar & Mondal, (2018) in their study enumerated the warning signs of IA to include the following:

- Preoccupation with the internet (thoughts about previous online activity or anticipation of the next online session);
- Use of the Internet in increasing amounts of time in order to achieve satisfaction;
- Repeated, unsuccessful efforts to control, cut back, or stop internet use;

- Feelings of restlessness, moodiness, depression, or irritability when attempting to cut down the use of the internet;
- Online longer than originally intended;
- Jeopardized or risked loss of significant relationships, job, educational, or career opportunities because of internet use;
- Lies to family members, therapists, or others to conceal the extent of involvement with the internet;
- Use of the internet is a way to escape from problems or to relieve a dysphoric mood (e.g., feelings of hopelessness, guilt, anxiety, and depression);
- Feeling guilty and defensive about internet use;
- Feeling of euphoria while performing internet-based activities; and
- Physical symptoms of IA such as Carpal tunnel syndrome (pain and numbness in hands and wrists); Dry eyes or strained vision; backaches and neck aches; severe headaches; sleep disturbances; pronounced weight gain or weight loss (Kumar & Mondal, 2018).

The functionality of the internet has been expanded mainly because of the emergence of mobile technologies, which provide an easy way to gratify their urges, thus paving a path to addictive internet use, that is, internet addiction (Wong et al., 2015). Internet addiction is a behavioural problem that has gained increasing scientific recognition in the last decade, with some researchers claiming it is a "21st Century epidemic" (Kuss & Griffiths, 2014). One of the warning signals of IA is the time spent on the internet by individuals. American Psychiatric Association (APA, 2013) suggests that when individuals are continuously engaged in playing internet games, over some time, the gaming prompts a neurological response of feeling pleasure or reward, ultimately resulting in addictive behaviour. In addition, Shapira et al. (2003) documented that excessive use of the internet longer than expected is more likely to result in addictive behaviour.

Some studies mentioned loss of control of using internet leading to neglecting work and academics, and also shows symptoms of craving when a person is offline (Tran, et al. 2017). Spending excessive time on the internet negatively affects the daily life of young people. Various types of online activities, such as online gaming, social networking, online gambling, online shopping, and virtual sex, are related to IA (Wu, et al. 2015). Hassan, et al (2020) studied internet addiction among young adults in Bangladesh and found that the overall prevalence of internet addiction was 27.1%. the study also found that internet addiction rate was 28.6% in the subgroup 19–24 years and 23.5% among 25–35 years old. Olawade, et al (2020) studied internet Addiction among university students during covid-19 lockdown: case study of institutions in Nigeria. The results indicated that boredom was a key factor that had an impact on IA. The study concluded that the closure of schools, restriction of movement, reduced engagements, and seizures of allowances/stipends during the lockdown made the students vulnerable to IA.

A study conducted in six Asian countries reported that the prevalence of IA varies from 5% to 21% (Mak, et al. 2014). Even within the same country, there is a marked difference in the prevalence of IA due to diverse screening scales with inconsistent cut-off scores. For example, Mathew and Krishnan (2020) reported that IA can reduce the young generation's productivity and cause cognitive dysfunction, poor academic performance and physical, mental and behavioural disturbances. The extant research so far has covered the consequences of IA on depression and students' academic performance (Lopez-Fernandez et al., 2014). A study conducted on 200 college students in India, found that IA substantially impacts anxiety and depression and seriously affects their family relations and social life (Kumar & Mondal, 2018).

Budak, et al, (2015) studied level of IA among 596 university students and found that, 246 (41.3%) were mild addicts, 91 (15.2%) were moderate addicts, and 259 (43.5%) were not addicted to Internet use. The study by Raveendran, et al (2021) on internet addiction among students of medical college in North Kerala revealed that the prevalence of internet addiction was 59%. About 113 (49.8%) students were average online users (mild addiction), 19 (8.4%) students were experiencing occasional and frequent problems (moderate addiction) and 2 (0.8%) severely addicted students. Most of the study population-initiated internet use between the ages of 16 -18 years, 89 (39%) (Raveendran, et al 2021).

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design and questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents from their respective classrooms. The questionnaire adopted Internet Addiction Scale by Young, (1998) (Appendix I). Data was collected from 305 undergraduate students of LIS in Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port-Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. the questionnaire is made up of four sections: section a is on biographical data of the respondents. Section B is on reasons the undergraduate students use the Internet. Section C is on the frequency of Internet use, and the section D on Internet Addiction Scale which consist of 20 items on a five-point Likert scale (from "1 - To a Very Great Extent to 5 - No Extent"). Data collection started June 2022 and ended August 2022. In total 360 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the students out of which 305 completed copies were returned with response rate of 84.7% which was judged as appropriate.

Method of data analysis

Data analysis was conducted using Microsoft excel software. Descriptive statistics such as mean was used to establish the extent of Internet addiction among LIS students was used. The scores of The Young's Internet addiction test were compiled and severity impairment index was calculated. The criterion mean that was used for this study was 3.00. This implies that any item with a mean score of 3.00 and above was accepted, while any item with a mean score that is below 3.00 was rejected.

Results

Table 1: Biographical data of respondents

Name of University	No of respondents	Percentage
Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State.	120	39.3%
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port-Harcourt, Rivers State	185	60.7%
Total	305	100%
Level of Study		
100 level	79	25.9
200 level	103	33.8
300 level	93	30.5
400 level	30	9.8
Total	305	100%
Gender		
Male	139	45.6%
Female	166	54.4%
Total	305	100%

Out of the 305 respondents, 185 (60.7%) indicated as students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port-Harcourt, Rivers State, while 120 (39.3%) respondents indicated as students of Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State. A breakdown according to level of study revealed that 103 (33.8%) indicated as 200 level students being the highest followed by 93 (30.5%) respondents who indicated as 300 level students, 79 (25.9%) indicated as 100 level students, and 30 (9.8%) indicated as 400 level students. Regarding gender distribution, more than half (166: 54.4%) indicated as female students, while almost half (139: 45.6%) indicated as male students (Table 1).

Table 2: Reasons for using the Internet

s/n	Reasons for using the Internet	Agree		Disagree	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	Chat rooms	198	64.9%	107	35.1%
2	Social networking	276	90.5%	29	9.5%
3	Course/assignment	177	58.0%	128	42.0%
4	Read/post news	102	33.4%	203	66.6%
5	For getting into relationships online	122	40%	183	60%
6	Watching videos	208	68.2%	97	31.8%

7	Playing mobile games	189	62.0%	116	38.0%
8	Downloading music or videos	217	71.1%	88	28.9%
9	Email communication	164	53.8%	141	46.2%
10	Instagram	192	63.0%	113	37.0%

When asked reasons for using the internet, results in Table 2 shows that 198 (64.9%) of the respondents agree that they used the internet to enter chat rooms. The majority (276: 90.5%) also agree that they used the internet to connect to social media platforms. More than half (177: 58.0%) of the respondents agree that they used the internet for course/assignment. The majority (203: 66.6%) of the respondents disagree that they used the internet to read or post news. The majority (183: 60%) also disagree that they used the internet for getting into online relationships. The majority (208: 68.2%) agree that they used the internet to watch videos. The majority (189: 62.0%) also agree that they used the internet to play mobile games. The majority (217: 71.1%) agree that they used the internet to download music and videos. More than half (164: 53.8%) of the respondents agree that they use the internet for email communications. Higher number (192: 63.0%) also agree that they use the internet for Instagram. This shows that the undergraduate students of LIS used the internet for reasons such as enter chat rooms, connecting to social media platforms, to do course or assignment, watch videos, play mobile games, download music and videos, email communications, and Instagram.

Frequency of Internet use

Results in Figure 1 shows that the majority (214: 70.2%) of the respondents indicated that they used the internet several times a day. Followed by those who indicated using the internet once a day (62: 20.3%). While, only 29 (9.5%) indicated using the internet occasionally. No respondent indicated to have never used the internet. The results indicate that the LIS students used the internet several times a day for one reason or the other.

Extent of Internet Addiction among LIS Students**Table 3: Extent of Internet Addiction among LIS Students**

Statements	VGE (5)	GE (4)	ME (3)	SE (2)	NE (1)	\bar{x}
I stay online longer than I intended	101	89	73	22	20	3.75
I neglect academic work to spend more time online	91	111	50	34	19	3.72
I prefer the excitement of the Internet to intimacy with mine classmates	80	93	78	22	32	3.55
I establish new relationships with fellow online users	77	109	82	17	20	3.68
My acquaintances complain to about the amount of time I spend online.	94	87	67	54	20	3.76
My grades or schoolwork suffer because of the amount of time I spend online.	104	76	90	20	15	3.77
I check mine e-mail before something else that I need to do.	56	40	23	98	88	2.60
My academic work suffers because of the time I spent on the Internet.	102	89	72	34	8	3.80
I become defensive or secretive when anyone asks me what I do online.	77	69	72	80	7	3.42
I block out disturbing thoughts about my life with soothing thoughts of the Internet.	63	74	104	49	14	3.39
I find that I find myself anticipating when I will go online again.	122	89	78	16	-	4.04
I fear that life without the Internet would be boring, empty or joyless.	100	75	91	33	6	3.75
I snap, yell or act annoyed if someone bothers me while I am online.	88	94	78	29	16	3.69
I lose sleep due to late night log-ins.	96	109	49	36	5	3.74
I feel preoccupied with the Internet when offline, or fantasize about being online.	83	99	19	72	32	3.42
I find myself saying "just a few more minutes" when online.	140	89	23	41	12	4.00
I try to cut down the amount of time I spend online.	108	69	62	40	26	3.63
I try to hide how long I have been online.	67	77	21	87	53	3.06
I choose to spend more time online over going out with classmates.	90	108	24	75	8	3.65
I feel depressed, moody or nervous when I am offline, which goes away when I am back online	69	72	84	80	-	3.43
Aggregate Mean = 3.59	Criterion Mean = 3.00					

Note: Very Great Extent (VGE), Great Extent (GE), Moderate extent (ME), Some Extent (SE), No Extent (NE).

Data presented in Table 3 reveals that the aggregate mean of 3.59 is higher than the criterion mean of 3.00, which is an indication that the extent of internet addiction among LIS students is high.

Scoring from the extent of Internet Addiction 20 items

The IAT total score is the sum of the ratings given by the examinee for the 20 items responses. Each item is rated on a 5-point scale ranging from 1-5. The maximum score is 100 points. The higher the score is, the higher is the severity of the problem. Total scores that range from 0-30 points are considered to reflect a normal level of internet usage; scores of 31 to 49 indicate the presence of a mild level of internet addiction; 50 to 79 reflect the presence of a moderate level; and scores of 80 to 100 indicate a severe dependence upon the internet.

Out of the 305 respondents, 259 students (84.9%) were found to be addicted to internet on Young's internet addiction test (Young's IAT) (Table 4).

Table 4: Distribution of respondents with internet addiction on Young's IAT

Level of Internet addiction	IAT scores	Frequency N=305	Percentage
Normal users	0-30	46	15.1%
Mild addiction	31-49	132	43.3%
Moderate addiction	50-79	108	35.4%
Severe addiction	80-100	19	6.2%

Note: Scores below 30 points indicates normal level of Internet usage

Discussion of findings

Reasons for using the Internet

The results revealed that the undergraduate students of LIS used the internet for reasons such as enter chat rooms, connecting to social media platforms, to do course or assignment, watch videos, play mobile games, download music and videos, email communications, and Instagram. This finding agrees with findings of a recent study by Oo et al, (2021) who conducted a study on internet usage and internet addiction of medical students in universities of Myanmar and found that more than 60 percent of the students used to engage in several activities excessively such as emailing (17%), gaming (50%), watching movies (90%), social media (93%), chatting (78%), and studies (63%).

Frequency of Internet use

On frequency of use of the internet, the results revealed that the LIS students used the internet several times a day for different activities. This finding is consistent with the results from the literature (Salehi et al., 2014; Frangos et al., 2011). Research indicates that excessive internet use can lead to symptoms associated with addiction. For example, Balasubramanian and Parayitam (2023) studied the consequences of internet addiction among school and college students in India and found that time spent on the internet every day is positively related to IA and IA is positively related to time spent on networking, video streaming, short video apps, educational apps, chat apps, online shopping apps, money involved apps, etc. Many studies have been conducted to examine how academic performance is related to young people's internet use. The studies reported negative impacts such as most non-school hours are spent on the Internet or playing online games, not keeping up with assignments, missing classes, falling asleep in school, declining grades, failing a course, missing a social engagement, and dropping out of other social groups (clubs or sports) (Huang et al., 2009; Kim et al., 2009). Research on the relationship between internet use and the ability to focus attention showed that amount of time spent using the internet by young people was significantly related to higher ratings of distractibility for academic tasks (Levine et al., 2007). Excessive internet use also caused deficient self-regulation (LaRose et al., 2003), and poor performance at school (Clark et al., 2004). Kumar and Mondal (2018) reported that students who are found to be severe users of internet use a maximum of 3–4 h per day and they are not able to perform their responsibilities properly such as concentration on academics and developing social isolation owing to excessive use of the

internet. Similarly, Mariavinifa, Govindarajan and Felix (2021) reported that prevalence of Internet addiction was high among students who used internet for a longer time i.e. 5hours or more per day for social networking, communication, online gaming compared to those used for less than 5 hours per day and for academic purpose.

Extent of Internet Addiction among LIS Students

In the present study, out of the 305 LIS undergraduate students that participated in the study, 43.3% students reported mild addiction, 35.4% students reported moderate addiction and 6.2% reported severe addition. Mild addiction indicates that those students are average online users but they have to control over their usage. Moderate addiction indicates that those students are experiencing occasional or frequent problems because of the internet. Severe addiction indicates that internet usage is causing significant problems in their life (IAT Manual, 2015). The results revealed that the extent of internet addiction among LIS students in the two universities in Nigeria is high. This finding is similar to a recent study by Zenebe, et al (2021) who studied the prevalence and associated factors of internet addiction among undergraduate university students in Ethiopia and found a high prevalence of internet addiction among Wollo University students. Chaudhari et al (2015) study also reported a higher overall prevalence of 58.87% and a lower prevalence of moderate and severe Internet addiction (7.45%) in western Maharashtra. The functionality of the internet has been expanded mainly because of the emergence of mobile technologies, which provide an easy way to gratify their urges, thus paving a path to addictive Internet use (Wong, Yuen, and Li, 2015). The present study shows internet addiction is common among the undergraduate students and adequate steps have to be taken to prevent the students from falling into severe addiction which is considered as a mental health issue. Knowledge regarding the safe use of internet has to be provided to students.

Conclusion

As IA has the potential to result in psychological distress, anxiety, low esteem, aggression, and even suicide, it is necessary to examine the extent to which students engage in the Internet in terms of how much time they spend on unproductive and non-academic use. When students spend more time watching movies, listening to songs, chatting with friends, in addition to online learning, it can lead to IA if not checked and controlled. That is why this study investigated the extent of IA among the undergraduate students of two universities in Nigeria. The study therefore found that the IA is high among the students.

One of the ways to prevent the students from getting addicted to Internet is to provide them a digital gadget with educational App without entertainment app. Secondly, as the Internet has entered people's lives during the present digital era, it is more likely that the younger generation may misuse the available technology and get addicted to the net. To avoid this, the parents must educate their children about the dangers of IA and communicate to them to use the Internet for productive and business purposes.

Moreover, counsellors can collaborate with health professionals to organize programmes aimed at educating students regarding the safe use of Internet.

Findings will inform educational authorities to develop different strategies and programmes to intervene in the problematic internet use among the students.

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